

ACTS OF SOLIDARITY TO FIGHT SOCIO-ECONOMIC INEQUALITY - SOLIDARITY PRACTICE IN SLOVAKIA

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Abstract

The recent economic and fiscal crises have increased socio-economic inequality. Across Europe, there are policies and practices that have been successful in tightening these inequalities and divisions based on solidarity. The main areas where solidarity has brought positive impacts are employment, health, education, and housing. These solidarity acts usually have in common civic participation and social innovations. The aim of this paper is to analyse a selected act of solidarity, which is being developed in the Slovak Republic, the related outcomes and the policy developments. The main method used is a structured interview with organizations involved in realization of the programme and also with participants of the programme. The selected case study of solidarity act in Slovakia deals with increasing the financial literacy using social innovations in community education and is analysed in 6 areas (democracy, pluralism, transparency, social and political impact, recognition and scalability). The principal conclusion points out that the best solidarity acts are such that teach people how to change their behaviour in order to stop being dependant on public support and social services.

Points for Practitioners: *the paper analyses a case study of solidarity act in the field of education, the methodology of the program analysed in the case study can be adapted internationally (it has already spread across to the Czech Republic). The policy makers could use the programme and implement it as a way of community education, especially in vulnerable communities (e.g. children from orphanages, single parents, seniors, youth with fewer opportunities etc.) for combating social exclusion and poverty, as it has proven so. The paper shows results of the programme in the past 8 years.*

Key words: *solidarity, social innovation, public services*

JEL Classification: H43, H44

1. Introduction

The recent crisis has indirectly contributed to questioning the efficiency of financial markets and democratic institutions at European and national levels. Recent data from the Eurobarometer shows a continuous decrease in the trust levels that citizens from the European Union have on national governments and parliaments, radically decreasing in more than 25 points in the last six years (European Commission, 2013). Several social scientists have argued that the social and economic inequalities in the new global order are contributing to civil social reactions, based on solidarity, aiming to achieve a better society for all (Touraine, 2007; Wright, 2010).

The recent economic and fiscal crises as well as post-crisis policies of austerity have increased socio-economic inequality and spatial differences between and within the EU member states. Even those societies that have not been subjected to an explicit austerity agenda have been shaped by media debates on questions of redistribution and a new politics of core and periphery. The central argument and justification for the solidarity acts is that, while the economic crisis has generated new spatial inequalities (at European, national, regional and local level), there are policies and practices that have been successful in tightening these inequalities based on solidarity. Although there are several researchers dealing with the issues of social innovations aiming at solving the problems of public sector in providing public services that soothe the inequalities (e.g. Nemeč, 2008; Voorberg et al., 2015), the research on solidarity-based acts are rather scarce.

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Solidarity as human sentiment showing concern for others has come to pre-eminence in several social sciences (sociology, psychology, philosophy, economy) treated at both descriptive and normative dimensions. Such sides can be seen, however as the ones of the same coin seeing the norm as in part emerging from practical social and historical solidaristic activities and movements. The discussions and debates around solidarity have tried to seek to foreground key features of solidarity relations that are normatively desirable by reflecting on facts of actually existing relationships. Current theorists of solidarity such as Baryertz (1999) also distinguish between the uses that we make of the term solidarity – factual and normative. They elaborate on the fact that the normative use of solidarity implies an obligation to different individuals to help each other in case of need. Baryertz (ibid) puts forward different roles that solidarity plays, namely: as a feeling of human fraternity, as a sort of “cement” that provides cohesion to society, the sense that arises when a group stands for common goals normatively involving a reference to justice and also the use referred to the welfare state to be guaranteed between members of the same community/nation state.

Since the introduction of the concept of solidarity as a development of the ideal of fraternity invoked by the French Revolution the term has been used in a variety of contexts, theoretical and political, and with a wide range of meanings (Gould, 2007). In this regards, sociology has sought to explain social order, social change and the core elements that contribute to the emergence of society through the analysis of different models of solidarity (Durkheim, 1964; Subašić, et al., 2008), whilst solidarity explained by philosophy is related to normative theories about goodness and justice (Habermas, 1990; Rawls, 1999).

Cognitive theory has stated the existence of strong feelings of solidarity within a certain group which are coupled with opportunistic behaviours towards other groups (Lindenberg, 1998; 2006). Importantly, transnational networks of solidarity have been identified which do function differently and where it is to be expected that people help each other beyond a criterion uniquely based on rational theory (Gould, 2007).

The debate whether acts of solidarity can go beyond egoistic and selfish based explanations is still a vivid one. In this sense, many other authors have already discussed the limitations of Rational Choice approaches to fully understand the complexity of human behaviour, and more specifically solidarity acts. For example Elster (2007) analyses altruistic behaviours and points out the limitations of the rational choice perspective. Sen (1977, 2004), also argues how solidarity or similar concepts like sympathy and commitment (as he takes Adam Smith concept from the Theory of Moral Sentiments) needs to be at the centre of explanations for economic and human behaviour, otherwise economic theory is only reduced to provide partial explanations about human behaviour. Mason (2000), among other authors, elaborates on the consideration of solidarity as mutual concern, normatively used to depict the relationship among a moral community and also implying an eventual need for mutual aid bringing the term close to the idea of that “solidaristic action cannot be demanded, but only appealed for” (Gould, 2007).

Since the 1990s, several scholars (e.g. Osborne and Gaebler, 1993; Bailey, 1999; Nemeč et al, 2012) started to analyse in which ways public management could become more efficient and could avoid negative side effects that the introduction of market based measures might have. Since then, a wealth of conceptual and empirical research has been developed but there is certain consensus that more empirical research on the role that New Public Management (NPM) gives to the state and citizens is needed in order to assess the impact of this model (Van de Walle and Hammerschmid, 2011). Nemeč (2010) goes further into the analysis of the NPM and affirms that the paradigm of New Public Management has been surpassed, but sets as a future target for any government operation governing by predictable, reliable and coherent, open and transparent, accountable and responsible bureaucracy, using evidence and consultation based policy making and simultaneously properly managing efficiency, economy and effectiveness.

Other fields of research have also recently shifted to analyse until which extent civil society is effectively responding to social needs by the means of defining new relationships with the state and the market. In his analysis of Real Utopias, Wright (2010) has put special focus on identifying the potential of social power, and the diverse connections that are defined regarding the state and market. Wright highlights that both state and market power are insufficient to adequately address social problems, but highlights a series of real utopias which demonstrate the power of people to innovate and find ways to organize themselves to transform and overcome their social condition or just to fulfil more effectively their needs regardless of the state or the market. Also, Valentinov and Vaceková (2015) argue, the civil sector and its non-profit non-governmental organizations (NGOs) bring social justice to rural area, i.e. NGOs help to solve spatial inequalities.

Solidarity acts are entwined social innovations which can be defined as new ideas (products, services and models) that simultaneously meet social needs (more effectively than alternatives) and create new social relationships or collaborations (Mulgan, Tucker, & Sanders, 2007). Bason (2010) emphasizes in this regard the engagement of social agents in these social innovations which leads to an increasing collaboration among the different stakeholders involved overcoming organizational boundaries and legal frameworks. Nemeč et al. (2015) underscore that different from innovation in general, social innovation targets meeting social demands and thus aims at the value of the social and political outcomes for the main stakeholders Thus, addressing major

societal challenges through social innovation requires involving all social actors, including the public and private sectors, social economies and the citizens themselves.

Several projects are given as examples of best practices in the initiative Social Innovation Europe, launched by the European Commission, these projects cover policy areas such as employment, health, education, and housing, among others that highlight social transformation towards greater social justice. Within the research on social innovation, some authors (e.g. Stephens et al., 2010), pointed out that financial exclusion and high indebtedness has also been raised, especially in the context of the recent economic crisis. The Financial Literacy Programmes developed by the Joint Centre for Housing Studies at Harvard University are illustrative of successful initiatives for groups with low educational levels. These programmes have demonstrated to have a positive impact on financial decision-making for those attempting to access suitable housing. Specifically, programme participants were taught how to acquire relevant essential knowledge about the credit and mortgage market, thereby improving their future chances of successful housing outcomes. It is showed how financially literate people are taught to make better decisions about their mortgages, as well as having more knowledge about how to avoid potential fraud as far as public or private housing is concerned. Such findings are consistent with other studies in the scientific literature in the area of financial decision-making, as well as the research on how to promote social cohesion from the bottom up (INCLUDE-ED, 2006-2011). Therefore, we chose a successful case study of solidarity act in Slovakia that deals with increasing the financial literacy in community education based programme.

2. Methodology

The aim of this paper is to analyse a selected act of solidarity, which is being developed in the Slovak Republic, the related outcomes and the policy developments. When fulfilling the goal, we also present preliminary research information collected within the frames of SOLIDUS project - Solidarity in European societies: empowerment, social justice and citizenship.

The methodology is fully consistent to the methodology of SOLIDUS research project. The selection of case studies followed these criteria:

- There is clear evidence regarding success (social and/or political impact).
- The solidarity practices must be related to spatial dimensions (local, regional or national) they must be related to group identity identification (i.e. age, ethnic background, religion, gender, income group).
- There is balance between top-down and bottom-up cases selected (i.e. there are cases with citizens, end-users or NGO stakeholders involved, cases with governmental institutions involved and cases with both involvements).
- There is balance among the different policy areas (i.e. housing, employment, health, education and civic engagement).
- At least half of the case studies conducted will be oriented to the fight against poverty and social exclusion.

A main requirement, in relation to the objectives of the SOLIDUS project, is that the cases selected have achieved significant impacts in their particular field of action. With the criteria in mind, we identified 16 cases in Slovakia using content analysis of databases, webpages and other relevant documents. Out of these 16 cases, 5 were chosen by the research leader in Spain for in-depth analysis using a structured interview. We have followed an interview protocol where all types of involved stakeholders were interviewed. Following these criteria, several cases were identified (Table 1):

Table 1: List of cases studies – solidarity based acts

Case	Spatial dimension	Initiated as	Stakeholders	Policy area	Fight against poverty and social exclusion
Away from benefits to paid employment	local, regional	Top-down	municipality, regional agency, NGOs, companies, citizens	employment	yes - inclusion of long-term unemployed
The Twelve Month Project	local	Bottom-up	informal group of 15 young people, children with disabilities (auditory, physical, mental or autism), NGO	education, health	yes - inclusion of disadvantaged children

Social housing - Kojatice	local	Bottom-up	citizens, municipality	NGO, housing	yes - fighting poverty of Roma citizens and their social inclusion
Against corruption	national	Bottom-up	NGO, citizens	civic engagement	partially -fighting corruption, thus saving money
School of Family Finance	national coordination, local implementation	Bottom-up	NGOs, communities	education	yes - education in financial literacy for communities like Roma, children from orphanage, seniors, single mothers, etc.

Source: author

Due to the limited scope of the paper, we provide an in-depth analysis only of one case, namely the School of Family finance which has been a successful education programme for various excluded and/or vulnerable communities.

As set by the project leader, we follow 6 areas in the analysis of a successful case of solidarity act: democracy, pluralism, transparency, social and political impact, recognition and scalability.

- Democracy - the participation of all members of an organization in governance and decision-making processes is considered as organizational democracy (Cloke and Goldsmith, 2002; Manville and Ober, 2003). Democracy is a relevant variable because it influences in economic development and social improvements. Thus, citizens can express their voice (Hirschman, 1970), increasing the successful of their organizations, governments and States. So deliberative democracy is the best practice to manage societies and also a current citizens demand.
- Pluralism - diversity and pluralism in our societies is continuously increasing, which means that cultural, ideological, religious, and other identity diversities are more and more frequent in a real heterogeneous society (Touraine, 2007). In terms of members' composition of an organization, this diversity is a considered as a competitive advantage. Actually, diversity together with democratic decision-making processes enriches the organization, accumulating more social capital and, consequently more effective and successful actions (Putnam, 1993).
- Transparency - transparency and accountability is now a citizen's claim as a result of public's lost confidence in the institutions, also affecting to NGOs and other third sector organizations. In this regard, the transparency of NGOs has acquired a prominent role in recent years, especially after the economic crisis and specifically for NGOs which are working for reducing inequalities and to respond to social needs (García-Mainar & Marcuello 2007, Baur & Schmitz, 2012).
- Social and political impact - social impact is understood as the social improvements achieved as a consequence of implementing a particular project or action (Sorde-Marti, 2016) and political impact as the institutional repercussions of this project or action.
- Recognition - the social recognition of an NGO, such as having received any award, allows them to still have greater social visibility and provides powerful incentives to continue their work (Osborne & Plastrik, 1997), being able to generate political impact remarkable.
- Scalability - in order to address the spatial dimension, we will look at the reach of the organization analysed, as well as the reach of the solidarity action. Many organizations start local, through a targeted community based action, and later grow to different territories. The relationship between success (in terms of social improvements of peoples' lives) and scalability should be addressed.

3. Selected Case of Solidarity in Slovakia – School of Family Finance

The School of Family Finance (SFF) is a programme run by Children of Slovakia Foundation aimed at increasing financial literacy and thus improving the lives of the participants. The School of Family Finance is the first community project about financial literacy in Slovakia with accreditation from the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic. The project brings a new dimension to the community and changes its view on finance. After completion of the course the participants are more aware of their personal responsibility for their financial behaviour. Socially disadvantaged citizens, senior citizens, children from orphanages, clients of crisis centres and other groups of citizens have the opportunity to realize how their

decisions affect their financial situation. The seminars are organized throughout the year and are provided by trainers for the community. The seminars are free and education is in accordance with The School of Family Finance methodology. The topics of the seminars are chosen based on the needs and interests of the participants; these include topics like looking for a job, labour issues, taxes, fees, levies, life values and money, personal and family budget, how to communicate with financial institutions, modern payment instruments, credit, loans, payments, insurance as financial services, consumer protection, basics of investment etc.

In the words of the project manager (PM) the reasons for this project arose due to: "the low financial literacy of people in the Slovak Republic - in the period after 1990 a new system of the functioning of the state came into being prior to which the people had enjoyed "the security" guaranteed by the state and limited financial products offered by one bank; the market changed and the people failed to respond to those market changes (the elderly were unable to adapt and teach the young ones); new banking products appeared along with non-banking sector companies such as Drukos and people were bewildered by the choices, were easily duped and fell prey to fraudsters. In addition, changes of values in society occurred whereby one capitalized on one's fellow citizen's naivety, changes right up to the political elite whereby they created laws designed for those who swindled and robbed others (a fish rots from the head down)."

In its 8th year, the programme brings positive outcomes, in following text we map the 6 pre-defined areas.

Democracy

The project has created the following authorities:

- Project Manager and Coordinator from Children of Slovakia Foundation (CSF).
- Donor – Provident, Ltd. who appointed a person to communicate with CSF.
- Lecturers - give feedback based on seminars with participants.
- A group of methodologists – disseminate methodologies based on feedback.

Strategy and strategic decisions are jointly prepared and executed by the methodologists, the PM and Provident. To quote the PM: "CSF responds to changes and the lecturers' opinions in the communities, respond to participant and lecturer feedback, annually modify the methodology based on evaluation meetings and respects the needs of the community. From the community, the lecturers give feedback at review meetings held once a year, where all are present (CSF Project Manager, lecturers, methodologists and Provident). The review meeting covers assessment of the results, amendments to methodology and discusses the further development of the project."

Pluralism

The project includes stakeholders from private and third sectors, the CSF tries to establish cooperation with public sector, too, but communication with public administration (e.g. the Central Office of Labour, Social Affairs and) failed.

Plurality can be seen also in the target groups of SFF project, the project is designed for various groups: children, young people aged 15 and over, and adults in vulnerable communities (children from children's homes, children fostered out from children's homes, clients from crisis and community centres, mothers on maternity leave, senior citizens), but also adults in important roles - parents at home, adults in education - teachers, educators.

Transparency

The project is financed by a private donor, Provident, who agreed on transparent rules of providing funding to the lecturers who come from various NGOs.

The last finished year - the seventh year of the programme School of Family Finances was announced on 15th September 2014 on the websites of both CSF and SFF, and 31 applications were received. The CSF Management Board approved 23 organizations on 15th January 2015. The total sum allocated for the supported grants was 22,630.00 € (see Table 2).

During the project period those lecturers involved reported twice (February / March and November of the relevant year); an on-going report is sent in August and the final report, including financial, is sent in November.

Table 2 Results for the period 2008-2015

	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	TOTAL
Number of projects supported	12	35	19	23	26	24	21	23	183
Number of new lecturers	12	9	23	24	13	16	12	13	122
Number of participants	578	1 839	2 637	2 276	2 709	3 534	3 578	3 615	20 766
Number of hours taught	242	850	1129	1 257	1326	1 400	1 520	1 621	9345

Allocation of support in EUR	5 380	22 364	22 453	21 706	22 542	30 889	22 541	22 630	170 506
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Source: own elaboration based on internal documents of CSF

Social and political impact

The social impact can be seen in its importance for the community in the quotes of participants and lecturers, e.g.:

Instead of “I have to pay this back, I need to borrow more...” it’s “I even managed to put something by for harder times...” (Participant 1).

A community of incomplete families were provided with basic financial education in family finances. As a result, the families can plan personal and family finances better, reflect on and look for ways to increase their income, as well as how to save on costs by thorough planning and accounting. At the same time, they gain an overview on other important issues affecting families such as loans and consumer rights (Lecturer 1).

I have begun to value money more; I realized how to use it and to conduct financial transfers within the family budget (Participant 2).

In 2015, the composition of participants was from various communities:

Chart 1: Composition of participants in the 7th year of SFF

Source: own elaboration based on internal documents of CSF

The project has not yet had an impact on the political process at either local or a wider level, it has not initiated the formation of any specific public policy. The PM and CSF representatives visited the Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family, the Ministry of Education and the Office for Minorities, however, no one expressed the desire to enter into cooperation, because 1) they observed that Provident figured there as a donor and 2) would not accept the methodology developed by experts which could be disseminated is applicable in practice. They displayed an unwillingness to cooperate on the product as they wanted to apply their own methodology. Yet another problem perceived by the PM was the non-acceptance of the third sector by the government. The situation is different in the Czech Republic. Under the name “Alphabet of Family Finances”, the SFF has since spread to the Czech Republic where there is support from the government and the services have been utilised by municipal authorities for the retraining of local government officers. Third sector

professionals help in the deleveraging of individuals in the Czech Republic where there is a much more advanced network for debt relief. According to the PM, it is a characteristic of Slovaks that "they do not want to cooperate, they do not search in unison, and everyone wants to have their own methodology." On the other hand, the project has not been influenced by any political decisions.

Recognition

SFF has not received any awards, but it is the first and only Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport accredited community project.

The programme has good media coverage:

- nanicmama.sk – a website for mothers on maternity leave – articles and discussions on financial literacy,
- via Global Money Week – publishing results that local media respond well to,
- publicity through local media and through lecturers who are obliged to do so by the grant,
- in 2012 one of the methodologists appeared on Dobré ráno ("Goog morning" – a TV programme in a national media), the topic was how not to get in debt.

Scalability

The SFF covers whole of Slovakia – it is a national project which is nevertheless received by local communities via local NGOs. Coordination is carried out by foundation: communication with lecturers who must be trained in the accredited programme; lecturers working in the communities receive a financial contribution financed through a grant.

The project is nationwide, whereby it reflects the inequalities between communities; the main functioning mechanisms are:

Grant round - supports a defined number of organizations implementing activities in their community; trained, certified lecturers can apply for a grant amounting to 650 – 2,150 € by sending a project application in which they specify a community (target group with which they work, the activities and budget); it takes three months for a decision to be made whether support for the project will be granted or not; then a maximum 9 months for implementation of the project.

Services to people – by request, an organization that has an interest in education addresses the CSF, which then puts the organisation in contact with a lecturer who implements a workshop in the community (more flexible than the grant round as the lecturer can be teaching within two weeks and is not required to write a project application; the activity and budget is provided by CSF); can respond flexibly to demand; this option was added in the fourth year of the programme.

Global Money Week – represents worldwide activities (celebration and social awareness of financial literacy), participation of lecturers, each year there is a new theme to which lecturers organise a week of activities aimed at increasing of financial literacy.

The School of Family Finance has gone global - in 2010 it spread to the Czech Republic under the name Alphabet of Family Finances.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of the selected case study "School of Family Finance" we can conclude that despite the fact, that the private donor, Provident, is a limited company providing short-term loans with rather high interest rate but still within the range limited by the Slovak legislation, we can state that the analysed case is a solidarity act aimed at helping citizens endangered by social exclusion.

The programme has brought positive change into lives of many participants by increasing their financial literacy. The participants from various communities (including marginalised and risk groups, e.g. seniors, orphans, Roma) learnt how to make better decisions about their finance which help them to prevent indebtedting or in case they already had been indebted, thanks to the SFF they learnt how to pay off their debts.

The act of solidarity has been initiated by third sector, which is in line with research on social innovations in Slovakia (Nemec et al., 2016; Nemec, Svidroňová, 2015). The government is rather reluctant to social innovations; they tend to reject risks and also from historical point of view, the government is not used to cooperate with citizens (Bakoš, Soukopová and Šelešovský, 2015) or third sector which is a precondition of any social innovation.

The research on the issues of solidarity within the SOLIDUS project has only started, the future steps are focusing on identifying drivers and barriers of solidarity acts and their scalability across the Europe.

Acknowledgements

The research SOLIDUS leading to these results received funding from the H2020 Programme of the European Commission under Grant Agreement n° 649489.

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